

Consistency Rules (CR) for UML Models

CR 1: Message Action must be defined as an Operation in Receiver's Class

```
context Message inv:
  self.receiveEvent.asType(InteractionFragment).covered->forAll(r|r.represents.type.
    asType(Class).ownedOperation->exists(op| op.name=self.name))
```

CR 2: The connected Classifier of the Association End should be included in the Namespace of the Association

```
context Association inv:
  self.memberEnd.size() > 0 implies self.memberEnd->forAll(p | p.type <> null
    implies p.type.namespace = self.namespace)
```

CR 3: AssociationEnds must have unique Names within the Association

```
context Association inv:
  self.memberEnd->forAll(p1,p2 : Property| p1 <> p2 implies p1.name <> p2.name)
```

CR 4: At most one AssociationEnd may be an Aggregation or Composition

```
context Association inv:
  self.memberEnd->size() > 0 implies self.memberEnd->select(p | p.aggregation.name =
    'composite')->size() <= 1 or self.memberEnd->select(m | m.aggregation.name =
    'shared')->size() <= 1
```

CR 5: A Class may use Unique Attribute Names

```
context Class inv:
  self.ownedAttribute->forAll(p1,p2:Property | p1 <> p2 implies p1.name <> p2.name)
```

CR 6: A Classifier may not belong by Composition to more than one Composite Classifier

```
context Property inv:
  (self.association <> null and self.aggregation.name='composite') implies (self.
    upper >= 0 and self.upper <= 1)
```

CR 7: A Package must have a non-empty unique name

```
context Package inv:
  self.packagedElement->forAll(e1,e2 | (e1 <> e2) and (e1.name <> '' and e2.name <>
    '')) implies (e1.name <> e2.name)
```

CR 8: An Interface can only contain Public Operations and no Attributes

```
context Interface inv:
  self.ownedAttribute->forAll(pr: Property| pr.association <> null or pr.visibility.
    name = 'public') and self.ownedOperation->forAll(o: Operation| o.visibility.
    name = 'public')
```

CR 9: No two Class Operations may have the same Signature

```
context Class inv:
  self.ownedOperation->forAll(o1,o2 : Operation | o1 <> o2 implies (o1.name <> o2.
    name or o1.ownedParameter->size() <> o2.ownedParameter->size() or o1.
    ownedParameter->collect(p1: Parameter | p1.type )->exists(t1: Type | o2.
    ownedParameter->collect(p2: Parameter | p2.type )->excludes(t1)) or o2.
    ownedParameter->collect(p3: Parameter | p3.type )->exists(t2: Type | o1.
    ownedParameter->collect(p4: Parameter | p4.type )->excludes(t2))))
```

CR 10: Operation Parameters must have unique Names

```
context Operation inv:
  self.ownedParameter->forAll(p1,p2: Parameter| p1 <> p2 implies p1.name <> p2.name)
```

CR 11: The Type of Operation Parameters must be included in the Namespace of the Operation Owner

```
context Operation inv:
self.ownedParameter->forall(p: Parameter | p.type <> null implies p.type.namespace =
self.owner.asType(Class).namespace)
```

CR 12: The Parent must be included in the Namespace of the Generalizable Element

```
context Generalization inv:
self.source->forall(e1: Element | e1.isKindOf(NamedElement) implies self.target->
forall(e2 : Element | e2.isKindOf(NamedElement) and e1.asType(NamedElement).
namespace = e2.asType(NamedElement ).namespace))
```

CR 13: An Operation has at most one return Parameter

```
context Operation inv:
self.ownedParameter->select(p : Parameter | p.direction.name = 'return')->size()
<= 1
```

CR 14: Every lifeline has to have a corresponding Class

```
context Lifeline inv:
self.represents.type.isTypeOf(Class)
```
